

BIPVBOOST PROJECT – BRINGING DOWN COSTS OF BUILDING-INTEGRATED PHOTOVOLTAIC (BIPV) SOLUTIONS AND PROCESSES ALONG THE VALUE CHAIN, ENABLING WIDESPREAD IMPLEMENTATION IN NEAR ZERO ENERGY BUILDING (nZEBs) IMPLEMENTATION.

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ABSTRACT: Building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) technology has the potential to significantly contribute to the achievement of the demanding energy efficiency targets set by the EU, however, its market uptake has been hindered by the difficulties of the industry in providing holistic solutions complying with key demands from decision makers and end-users. This market deployment depends critically on the achievement of ambitious targets in terms of cost reduction, flexibility of design, high performance, reliability, aesthetics, standardization and compliance with legal regulations. BIPVBOOST will implement medium-term cost reduction roadmaps, addressing the whole BIPV value chain and will demonstrate in real operation conditions the contribution of the technology towards mass realization of nearly Zero Energy Buildings. BIPVBOOST will therefore contribute to lowering the cost of multifunctional BIPV systems, limiting the overall cost with respect to traditional, non-PV, construction solutions and non-integrated PV modules. At least 17 demonstrated innovative solutions will result from the successful implementation of the BIPVBOOST project. Together with the large involvement from industrial partners in the consortium, a sound basis will be to pursue a 50% reduction of additional cost of BIPV modules in 2020 and 75% reduction in 2030, and thus a substantial increase of market deployment of BIPV technology.

Keywords: Building Integrated PV, Building Integration, Manufacturing and Processing

1 AIM AND APPROACH USED

BIPV has been considered as a key possible contribution from the PV industry to GHG emissions mitigation, especially taking into consideration the increasingly demanding legislation related to energy performance in buildings. The building sector provides the second largest untapped potential for energy savings after the energy sector itself, accounting for 40% of EU's final energy demand and 36% of CO₂ emissions in Europe. Moreover, using the building skin to generate electricity is a valuable means to save useful land space.

Building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) technology has therefore the potential to significantly contribute to the achievement of the demanding energy efficiency targets set by the EU. Market analysis¹ estimates that BIPV sector will reach revenues of around \$7 billion (6.11€ Billion) by 2024, growing at a CAGR of approximately 15% during 2018-2024. Within this framework, while Europe holds the largest share in the global BIPV market segmented into Asia-Pacific (APAC), Europe, North America, and rest of the world (ROW), PAC establishes as the fastest growing region in the global market, at a CAGR of approximately

17% during the forecasted period.

Despite this positive environment, BIPV yet remains a niche market. Its market uptake has been hindered in the past years by the difficulties of the industry in providing holistic solutions complying with key demands from decision makers and end-users. In this sense, it is a common perception that a joint industrial effort is needed to conceive and develop highly-efficient and multifunctional energy producing construction materials, in order to provide market opportunities at a world-wide level for the European photovoltaic and construction industry value chains. This market deployment depends critically on the achievement of ambitious targets in terms of significant cost reduction, flexibility of design, high performance, reliability in the long-term, aesthetics, standardization and compliance with legal regulations. Within this context, the main objective of BIPVBOOST project is to bring down the cost of multifunctional building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) systems, limiting the additional cost with respect to traditional, non-PV, construction solutions and non-integrated PV modules, through an effective implementation of short and medium-term cost reduction roadmaps addressing the whole BIPV

¹ Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) Market - Global Outlook and Forecast 2019-2024

<https://www.arizton.com/market-reports/building-integrated-photovoltaics-bipv-market>

value chain and demonstration of the contribution of the technology towards mass realization of nearly Zero Energy Buildings (nZEBs).

The ambition of this project is to demonstrate the key cost reductions required to implement BIPV technology in the real market, moving from a luxury and costly BIPV towards a mass-market and cost-effective approach with a clear focus on the ordinary built stock, that will require a deep energy renovation in the next decades. Therefore, a sound progress of Europe manufacturing industry towards the forefront of BIPV technology and installed capacity is expected as an outcome of the project.

2 SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

BIPVBOOST project has a large innovation potential based on the demonstration of BIPV modules, building skin products and manufacturing processes with a clear potential for cost reduction and at the same time providing high performance, production, reliability, aesthetics and multifunctional properties. The main exploitable innovation potential from the project can be gathered around the following categories:

- Flexible and automatic glass-glass BIPV modules manufacturing and quality control line: 1) tabber-welding for c-Si, 2) tabber-welding for back-contact cells, 3) string lay-up, 4) interconnection station, 5) in-line electroluminescence quality control.
- Portfolio of low-cost and aesthetically advanced glass-glass BIPV products based on c-Si, back-contact and a-Si technologies: 6) coloured c-Si based solutions for ventilated façades, 7) a-Si patterning solutions for skylights, ventilated façades and curtain walls, 8) bifacial modules for balustrades, 9) back-contact modules for walkable floors, curtain walls, etc.
- Roofing and façade solutions for the building skin: 10) multifunctional BIPV opaque façade cladding system, 11) enhanced roof systems with CIGS on metal modules, 12) enhanced façade systems with CIGS on metal, 13) low cost, click&go façade systems with glass-glass modules.
- Digital solutions for the BIPV value chain: 14) BIM-based software tool supporting process design, manufacturing and installation, 15) cloud-based BEMS including demand response and storage management, 16) fault detection and diagnosis tool, 17) Augmented reality app for pre-design stage.

3 RESULTS OR PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The outcomes of BIPVBOOST project are expected to deeply modify the current paradigm by contributing to establish a solid basis for a substantial increase of market deployment of BIPV. Among others, by reducing the

additional cost of BIPV systems in comparison with those of BAPV and traditional architectural products and demonstrating multifunctional building products to support a wider implementation in the framework of nZEBs related objectives.

BIPV modules developed within BIPVBOOST will fully comply with the strategic targets established by the “SET Plan – Declaration on Strategic Targets in the context of an Initiative for Global Leadership in Photovoltaics”². The specific targets defined are: 50% reduction of additional cost of BIPV modules in 2020 and 75% reduction in 2030, with regards to the reference cost in 2015

Additionally, the proposed building skin products will demonstrate cost reductions up to 50% at the end of the project and up to 80% by 2030. These cost reductions are expected to bring annual market growth from 15% to 25% in our high scenario, reaching an annual development of up to 3 GWp by 2025 and of 9.3 GWp by 2030 in Europe. Eventually, the project will also contribute to trigger the growth of the EU (BI)PV industry, along its value chain, by making it more competitive. Thanks to this market and industry stimulation, it is estimated that up to 61200-137000 jobs could be created during the 2020-2030 decade (120-44%).

4 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817991.

5 DISCLAIMER

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

² SET-Plan - Declaration on Strategic Targets in the context of an Initiative for Global Leadership in Photovoltaics (PV)

http://www.etip-pv.eu/fileadmin/Documents/SET_Plan/3_Declaration_of_intent_Photovoltaics.pdf